

Equilibrium is Not an Option - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the two main equations of the new 8T, and in particular the term of arbitrary variations to vanish into matter, alongside the ratio of net curvature and isomorphism to prime numbers, which propagate across the metric tensor, it is possible to refute equilibrium. The definition of equilibrium in a cosmological context is a static universe; In particular, it is possible to analyze two options, a collapse if the summation of net curvature is larger than the outward acceleration by distinct manifolds, and vice versa.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The major question is, whether there could be such a thing as static universe, and if there is, what is the mathematical construction of such cosmological state? Since in the 8T according to the main equation, (1.2) we have outward acceleration from areas of extremum curvatures, and at the same time, we have proven Bosons to be net curvature isomorphic to primes or one, given by the primorial in equations (1.4) to (1.43), those two inverse effects will, if one is intuition is on point, eventually determine the future of the manifold in cosmological scales. A cosmological equilibrium means that the summation of net curvature across the entire universe is exactly equal to the magnitude of the outward acceleration, to a perfect cancelation. Define a functor:

$$\mathfrak{h}: Top \rightarrow set$$

And sum in a set all the magnitude of the net curvature on the matrix tensor,

$$\Omega = [K_1 N_{v1} + \dots K_n N_{vn}] \quad (1.45)$$

Where the parameter summation $K_{1 \rightarrow n}$ is a scalar that denote the number of prime elements of certain magnitude. The set is than the summation of all curvature elements according to their distribution across the matrix tensor. By physical measurement, we also know that we have a certain magnitude for the term:

$$\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

So the equilibrium state will be achieved when and if those two terms will equalize:

$$\Omega - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

However, that state of equilibrium is not a reasonable option. That is for two reasons. The first, it builds upon the assumption that the set is finite, in reality it is not. There is uncertainty regarding Bosons propagation from fermions, as the arrow of time develops, more and more interactions of weaker overall magnitude manifest themselves, it is impossible to determine the set value. On the other hand, assuming the manifold packet is infinite; it means that more manifolds are getting into the packet that could affect the acceleration term, in such way that the more time in the packet, the stronger the acceleration, to ensure the term is still zero we can regard it as adiabatic variant. Two options are reasonable according to (1.46). First, the summation of all net curvature across the manifold is larger than the outward acceleration from areas of extremum curvatures; in that case, there will be manifold collapse:

$$\Omega - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} > 0 \quad (1.46.A)$$

The summation of all net curvature across the manifold is smaller than the outward acceleration from areas of extremum curvatures; in that case, there will be manifold expansion:

$$\Omega - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} < 0 \quad (1.46. B)$$

Since the interactions are getting weaker and weaker overtime, according to the principle of least variation, it is less likable that a collapse will accrue, as the manifold is getting colder with larger variation terms that indicate smaller ratios of net curvature to total curvature. If there could be a collapse scenario, it should be when the universe is experiencing the strongest amount of net curvatures, i.e. close to the singularity and creation of nuclei's. According to the 8T, and the primorial coupling constants series, equation (1.46.B) seems to describe a more reasonable option. This equation indicate that the outward pressure exhorted by a unknown in size, of distinct manifolds in the packet, is larger than the summation of net curvatures on the matric tensor, that is why the universe is expanding and not collapsing. We ignored the matter configuration in that analysis as we proven that the term describing fermions requires vanishing of curvature.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

That is in contrast to General Relativity framework, which associate morphism between fermion clusters and curvature. Overall, it seems unreasonable to think we can solve the equations of (1.46/A-B), and it was not the point of the paper. The point was to present the idea of rate of pressure from the packet, to be equal or not equal to the summation of net curvatures, as a simple model to which we can refer to in questioning the future of the universe.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)